

2.4. CONNECTING BUSINESS, RESEARCH AND EDUCATION COMMUNITIES

BOOSTING ENTREPRENEURSHIP AND ENTREPRENEURIAL SKILLS OF ACADEMIC COMMUNITY AT THE UNIVERSITIES OF ARMENIA

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ABSTRACT. *The article introduces the steps carried out for the reinforcement of entrepreneurship at Armenian universities and the main mechanisms for the enhancement and development of entrepreneurial skills of students and staff. The research has been done according to oral and written inquiry, information placed on the websites and social media pages of Armenian universities, as well as surveys. To this end, much funding has been and is still being invested by European and British organizations for fostering entrepreneurial education at Armenian HEIs and establishing co-creative hubs, the main aim of which is to create a favorable environment for young entrepreneurs and to give birth to innovative ideas through entrepreneurship or open innovation. To lay ground and build capacities for the digital and entrepreneurial education, special centres have been established in major Armenian cities where the competences of younger generation could be improved. Still there is an urgent need for the embedment of entrepreneurial component in the curricula and for the creation of a favourable ecosystem for research and innovation at Armenian universities.*

Key words: *entrepreneurship, entrepreneurial skills, Armenian universities, ecosystem, co-creative hubs*

These days we are experiencing the drastic developments of the Fourth Industrial Revolution. People are connected by mobile devices, with unprecedented processing power, storage capacity, and access to knowledge and possibilities to learn something new, acquire various skills and create unique things. All these possibilities will increase and develop in fields such as artificial intelligence, robotics, the Internet of Things, autonomous vehicles, 3-D printing, nanotechnology, biotechnology, and many other new fields.

To work, to be competitive and to improve one's career in this rapidly changing world, special 21st century skills are required and not only knowledge. As the keynote speaker Dr Neil Marshal noted in his speech during the conference held on 13 October, 2021 in Tsakhkadzor [5], “learning is no longer about knowledge. Yes, it gives a base, but now it's also about learning how to learn”. Additionally, he stated in his speech that our research, knowledge creation is no longer possible by sitting in the lab. It's no longer an individual activity but collaboration and networking. Nowadays university graduates need the 21st century skills that demand considerably more soft than hard skills. That's why universities should be responsive to the changes of the labour market, engage with industry, review and update the curriculum, teaching and learning approaches, boost collaborative research as well as enhance the entrepreneurial abilities of their students.

Many Armenian universities have already started serious steps towards these developments and are quite cognizant of the need to respond to it as quickly as possible. In the 2030 Development

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Draft Plan of the Education Law of Armenia, discussed during the period 14.02.- 01.03.2022 and given to the RA Government for approval, it is emphasized that there is an imperative need to bolster professional orientation, career guidance, set up relevant centers, introducing entrepreneurial training. Another very important imperative is to enhance the IT field, to intensively implement distant learning mechanisms and tools, to ensure the security of the virtual platforms, to enhance the innovative approaches to teaching and learning. In addition to this, the RA government responds to the European Commission's message, entitled "Rethinking Education", and considers work-based learning to be a strategic priority. Work-based learning, such as the dual approach, should be a central pillar of the vocational education and training system, with the aim of reducing youth unemployment, ensuring an easy transition from education to work, and developing the ability to respond to skills needed in the labor market (30). Special attention is also paid to the training of students in the fields of mathematics, natural sciences, engineering and information technologies (STEM), mastery of foreign languages, as well as the development of students' critical, analytical, innovative, independent and creative thinking. The total amount of STEM subjects in the RA general education programs is not enough, and more than half of the university students are involved in the fields of humanities, arts, management and law, while the share of ICT in the economy is constantly growing (24).

To support and assist Armenian universities for the mainstreaming entrepreneurship and innovation among the members of academic community, intensive European assistance has been provided throughout the recent years. Substantial funding in the development of entrepreneurial education has been provided by the GIZ program via EU4Business Innovative Tourism in Armenia project [7], Erasmus+ Capacity Building "INNOCENS," "SMART," "CONNECT," "FlexWBL" and "WBL4JOB" projects as well as British Council Creative Spark Programme [2] implemented by several Armenian and British institutions.

Due to the EU4Business Innovative Tourism in Armenia project Armenian HEIs and students have benefited in the main following spheres:

- Establishment of entrepreneurial relations among the students and community members,
- Exchange of International knowledge and support of high-tech researchers,
- Development and implementation of educational programs (BI and Customer Development, PM and Analytics, Growth Hacking, Enterprise Sales, UI/UX Design),
- Enhancement of capacities in Computer Science to engage in scientific activities in the fields of data science,
- Establishment / improvement of laboratories in some Armenian universities,
- Involvement of regional students in entrepreneurial and technological fields.

Erasmus+ Capacity building projects implemented in Armenia have had a great impact in reforming higher education and improving the educational spaces with modern equipment. Among the 30 implemented projects funded by the Erasmus+ program five projects are mainly related to entrepreneurial education and work-based learning.

The INNOCENS project [12] which ended in 2020, mainly aimed at enhancing innovation competences and entrepreneurial skills in engineering education through university-business cooperation in order to support creation of new enterprises, new jobs and economic growth in the partner countries. The main outcomes of the project are the establishment and exploitation of innovative centres (incubators) at National Polytechnic University of Armenia (NPUA) and National University of Architecture and Construction of Armenia (NUACA), creation of Business Mentor Teams and generation of innovative ideas, development and introduction of new courses: "Innovation systems", "Introduction to Engineering Entrepreneurship", "Engineering Entrepreneurship" and "Innovative Pedagogy and Innovative Teaching Methods".

The aim of the SMART project [14] was to encourage students' entrepreneurial intent and support open innovation approach in collaboration between companies and universities in creative,

supportive and motivating environment – SMART Caffes. As a result, two Armenian HEIs, Brusov State University and Gavar State University, benefited from the project and established centres for entrepreneurial education where various workshops, meetings and events were held to raise the entrepreneurial capacities of students. The project fostered the implementation of new teaching approaches, increased the entrepreneurial skills of teaching staff, and improved the quality of education. At the regional and national levels, the project created a new model of a public-private-people partnership and built a strong network of motivating environment for students in Eastern Partner Countries. Finally, yet importantly, the project fostered the integration of EaCP HEIs into the European Higher Education Area by using common tools for compatibility of EaCP higher education systems with the European ones.

Starting from 2021 three new Erasmus+ CBHE projects were funded which aimed at the development of entrepreneurial skills and work-based learning in Armenian HEIs: WBL4JOB/ Introducing work-based learning in higher education systems of Armenia and Moldova for better employability of graduates [17], FlexWBL/ Development of a flexible, innovative and practical framework for Work-based Learning in higher education of Armenia and Russia [8], and CONNECT/ Connecting universities-industry through smart entrepreneurial cooperation and competitive intelligence of students in MD, GE and AM [4]. The first two projects mainly focus on the creation of the work-based framework as well as development and implementation of supporting policy to enhance partnership between enterprises and HEIs and to increase graduates' employability. The CONNECT project aims at the reinforcement of university-industry relationship based on smart (multidimensional) entrepreneurial approach in HEIs from EaPCs and enhancement of students' and graduates' competitive intelligence (behaviours, skills, mindsets) and their ability to create jobs. The project intends to establish co-creative hubs, Smart Caffes, which would support students who generate, develop, market their own innovative ideas through entrepreneurship and/or open innovation in three EaPCs. This project has given a new breath to the academic community of consortium HEIs to improve the digital, entrepreneurial and art skills of students and staff by offering courses related to the mentioned fields. The members of this academic community are armed with great enthusiasm and skills to launch the activities of the Smart Caffe which will create a new environment for the young generation to co-create and build networking through enthusiastic teamwork, engagement and cooperation.

Serious investments have also been made by the Creative Spark Program of the British Council which has been funding projects since 2018 with Armenian and British partnership. All the projects implemented were aimed at the development of entrepreneurial and creative capacities of students at Armenian institutions. The beneficiary institutions are as follows:

1. American University of Armenia and Northumbria University, Newcastle;
2. V. Brusov State University, State Academy of Fine Arts in Armenia, University of Essex and Change School;
3. Armenian National Laboratories, CITY University of London and Change School;
4. Yerevan State University and Nottingham Trend University;
5. Armenian State Polytechnical University and the University of Southampton;
6. TUMO Centre for Creative Technologies and Norwich University of Arts;
7. FAST Foundation and Aston University, Birmingham.

Within the four-year long intensive undertaking the Creative Spark program greatly fostered the creation and establishment of 17 innovation centers (incubators), trained around 500 staff, implemented more than 100 courses directed to the development of different entrepreneurial skills, involved more than 15 000 students in the courses and prepared more than 500 students to take part in the competition “Big Idea Challenge” to develop innovative startups in four categories, which are Climate Change, Digital Technology, Social impact and Creative [3]. On the official website of the competition one can vote for the 12 Armenian finalists.

With the initiative of the RA government and the World Bank Enterprise Incubator Foundation (EIF) was established to enhance the IT/High-Tech development in Armenia [6]. It executes various activities such as ICT-related legal, business and educational reforms, investment channeling and creation of funding schemes for startups, individualized services and consulting for IT and Engineering companies, talent identification and workforce development. EIF provides different types of financial support to startups in various stages. With the support of EIF and the RA government Vanadzor Technology Center [16] and Gyumri Technology Center [10] were established to turn Vanadzor and Gyumri into regional and international high-tech centers which focus on assisting technology companies in business consultancy, mentoring, marketing and promotion, introduction to funding opportunities, and attracting the younger generation to create technology teams, start-ups and develop their innovative ideas into successful businesses within Armenia and internationally.

Another very important foundation which aims at building an ecosystem of innovation to lead scientists, technologists, and innovators in Armenia and beyond is the Foundation for Armenian Science and Technology [8]. It was founded with the initiative of an Armenian philanthropist Ruben Vardanyan who is also the leader of the “Future Armenian” movement endeavoring to bring creative, intellectual and progressive Armenians all over the world together around 15 main goals. FAST implements various projects related to education, research and commercialization. One of the projects implemented is the SciNova Program which developed a curriculum on “Research Design” and “Science Commercialization”. The curriculum introduces Masters and/or Ph.D. students in Armenia to the basics of conducting quality research and creating commercial value from scientific inventions. In 2021 it was first piloted in Armenian National Agrarian University (ANAU) and has recently organized training for trainers to introduce the courses at leading Universities of Armenia where STEM education is provided.

Since 2011 with the assistance of the representatives from Armenian Diaspora four TUMO Centers with 5 TUMO boxes operating in neighboring towns have been opened in Armenia (Yerevan, Dilijan, Gyumri and Stepanakert) with the aim of developing cutting-edge skills of the younger generation aged from 12 to 18 years to become competitive in the labour market [15].

Philip Morris International’s R&D Centre in Armenia, established in 2018 has adopted a unique approach to support the research and education ecosystem. In collaboration with EIF, PMI Science supports Masters and PhD programs, promotes Faculty team research projects, supports organization of scientific-technological conferences and conducts trainings. The centre has been cooperating with more than 125 scientists of leading scientific institutes and laboratories of the Republic of Armenia within the framework of the programs/projects implemented jointly with scientific institutions. Within the support of PMI Science R&D Center in Armenia, more than 120 Master’s, 40 PhD students and 62 Faculty research teams were awarded scholarships [13].

Apart from these centers there are also centres/hubs/incubators funded by various foundations such as Impact Hub [11], Agritech [1] and some other social innovation spaces founded in the capital city and other cities of Armenia in the recent years with a mission to support social impact projects and enterprises.

And yet, there are certain challenges that have to be overcome to create a thriving innovation ecosystem where people collaborate across organizations, cultures and generations to solve the grand challenges of our time. The main steps that have to be undertaken are as follows:

- development and promotion of an ecosystem of entrepreneurship in universities through private sector - university long-term and sustainable cooperation;
- establishment and development of legislative settings at all levels: university, private sector, state;
- enhancement and implementation of innovative approaches to teaching and learning;
- establishments of more creative spaces/hubs inside universities;

- regulation of intellectual property culture;
- integration of entrepreneurial component in academic programs to promote creative-entrepreneurial mentality, both among students and faculty.

In the long run, it is worth emphasizing the significance to create a collaborative spirit and to spread the responsiveness to meet the challenges and find reasonable solutions through creative mind and sensible solutions. Only through strategically designed and cutting-edge endeavors would it be possible to create a thriving community.

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